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Letter Blocks Intervention: A Holistic Approach in Addressing Spelling Difficulties in Elementary School

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to identify effective strategies and intervention tailored to address the spelling difficulties faced by particular group of learners. This study is quantitative research utilizing correlational research design to determine the relationship exist between spelling difficulties among the learners and the letter blocks intervention to the development of the learners (Grade4); to assess their progress in spelling difficulties (based on their scores on the Pre-test assessment. Moreover, with an overall mean score of 71.80 that demonstrate the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing learners' spelling sills; interactive and engaging methods, such as using letter tiles and other manipulatives object, significantly enhance students' spelling abilities by providing concrete experiences that support phonemic awareness and orthographic knowledge. This hands-on approach allows students to physically manipulate letters and sounds, reinforcing their learning through multi-sensory engagement. Educators might consider devoting additional attention to improve spelling difficulties among the learners through various interventions especially learners in primary level. The pre-test results revealed that the students' spelling abilities were below the expected level, indicating low proficiency. However, the post-test scores showed a marked improvement, with the students' scores rising after the letter blocks intervention was introduced. This suggests that the letter blocks intervention effectively enhances spelling abilities among Grade 4 learners.

Keywords: *letter blocks, spelling, elementary*

Introduction

Spelling is considered an essential component of written language and stands as an essential pillar in a student's literacy development, serving as a fundamental gateway to effective written communication and academic success. Learning to spell words correctly is considered an important activity due to the fact that spelling makes the reader understand what is written, so that the message is clear and understandable. It is an important skill which students must acquire before they could excel in the speaking, listening, reading and writing skills (Stainthorp & Ahmed, 2017).

In Saudi Arabia, Arabian students who learn English as a foreign language face different challenges during the process of learning of the four English language skills, especially writing and its component (spelling). It was found out that there are different causes of students' spelling errors such as the education system and university syllabus, students' learning attitude, and the interference between English and Arabic language. Research concludes that the spelling errors were caused negative impacts of their education system and syllabus, where the syllabus ignores the importance of spelling rules (Altamimi & Rashid, 2019).

In the Philippines, the study of spelling errors among Grade III pupils in Mindanao revealed a concerning finding: 89% of students made errors in their spelling during short essay assessments. This national and international assessments have revealed insufficient spelling skills among Filipino elementary students. This assert that poor spelling is one of the most prevalent academic issues encountered by pupils, and the problem persists from generation to generation. The problematic issue with spelling is the incorrect representation of words, comprehension and lack of phonemic awareness leading to misunderstandings of written communication (Apolog & Rosario, 2017).

In the Division of Davao del Norte, particularly at Clementa F. Royo Elementary School, a noteworthy observation surfaced during the Field Study courses. It became apparent that a considerable number of pupils, particularly those in higher grades (fourth to sixth grade), were encountering difficulties in spelling words that should ideally be within their mastery. The action research needed to be conducted since many students in higher grade 4 are struggling and faced challenges grappling with spelling rules, patterns, and the application of phonetics. The prevalence of such spelling difficulties among elementary school students signifies a notable hurdle, adversely affecting their overall academic performance and eroding self-confidence in language-related tasks.

In addition, in spite of the existence of related international studies addressing spelling difficulties, such as "Improving Students' English Spelling Ability Through Activity-Based Teaching-Learning" by Mahamuni (2022), "Letter Flip: On the Spelling Ability of The Grade III Pupils" by Apolog and Rosario (2017), and "Spelling Problems and Causes among Saudi English Language Undergraduates" by Altamimi and Rashid (2019), there remains a gap in the current action research. Since these studies are only offer valuable insights of spelling difficulty, the specific focus and interventions may not directly align with the needs of our target population, which includes students from grades 4 and not mention a hands-on activity as approach. Therefore, further exploration is needed to identify effective strategies and intervention tailored to address the spelling difficulties faced by this particular group of students. This proposal holds significant social value as it aims to provide a scholarly approach to offering practical solutions, thereby

addressing the spelling challenges encountered by grade 4.

This study aims to apply letter blocks in enhancing the spelling difficulties of Grade 4 learners. The researchers highlight the need for improved spelling abilities among Grade 4 learners who are at the instructional level and frustration level. The goal is to provide a foundation for schools' agendas and initiatives, ultimately enhancing reading programs.

Methodology

Research Design

The methodology used in this study was a quantitative-descriptive research design. This method is frequently used by professionals and educators to assess and enhance a teacher's pedagogy and practice (Clark et al., 2020). Thus, action research is a continuation of the critical introspection and contemplation that they use in their daily work as educators. Through transformation and reflection in a challenging circumstance within a mutually agreed ethical framework, action research blends theory and practices. Researchers work together on a series of tasks as part of the iterative action research methodology activities include reflective learning and active intervention. Action Research design is used in this research to determine if there is an enhancement in learners' spelling skills after implementing the design intervention (letter blocks) which includes mentoring and assistance aimed at improving their spelling difficulties over four months. After four months of intervention, the same participants took a post-test.

Respondents

The researchers used purposive sampling in which it refers to a group of non-probability sampling techniques in which units are selected because they have characteristics that you need in your sample. In other words, units are selected "on purpose" in purposive sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2023). Also called judgmental sampling, this sampling method relies on the researcher's judgment when identifying and selecting the individuals, cases, or events that can provide the best information to achieve the study's objectives.

In this case, the respondents for this research study are students from Grade 4 enrolled in the school year 2023-2024 at Clementa F. Royo Elementary School. This study involving 35 grade 4 from Clementa F. Royo Elementary School aligns with this guidance, balancing sample size and practicality. Using correlation quantitative to investigate the relationship between the frequency of using the Letter Blocks Intervention and students' spelling proficiency.

Procedure

The researchers utilized assessment before and after the implementation of intervention and innovation. The pre-test will measure the average of the students who are having difficulty with spelling before the implementation. The post-test will measure the knowledge and development of the learners through giving them the same set of spelling words in pre-test.

To gather the necessary data for this research, the following steps were taken by the researchers. First, before starting the study, the researchers sent a request to the principals of the schools where the participants were enrolled. Then, the researchers administered a pretest to determine the participants' initial spelling difficulties levels. Following the pretest, Letter Blocks was introduced, followed by a nine-weeks intervention period. At the end of the research process, a posttest was conducted using the same tool to evaluate any improvements in the participants' spelling difficulties levels after the intervention. The data from the pretest and posttest were then collected and tabulated.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data analysis is the process of making sense of numerical data through mathematical calculations and statistical tests. It helps to identify patterns, relationships, and trends to make better decisions. (Hotjar, 2018). The significant difference in this context refers to the measurable change in participants' performance from the pre-test to the post-test, assessed through statistical analysis to ensure that the improvement due to the Letter Blocks Intervention is not random but a result of the intervention itself. In analyzing, the researchers employ observation before and after the Letter Blocks Intervention has been implemented. The researchers identify the concept and finding the significance difference between the observed performance of the participants during the pre-test and post-test.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion regarding the effectiveness of the Letter Blocks intervention, a holistic approach designed to address spelling difficulties in elementary school students. The findings highlight the challenges in spelling instruction, the effectiveness of the intervention, and its impact on students' spelling proficiency.

Pre-Test Result

The data in Table 1 indicates that students experienced significant challenges in spelling before the intervention, with scores varying widely and an overall mean score of 37.74. This underscores the necessity for an intervention to improve spelling proficiency among the students. To support this, Fitton & Graham et al., (2017) stated that, it is important to comprehensive spelling instruction, integrating phonemic awareness, phonics, and morphological strategies to improve literacy skills. The research suggests that students struggling with spelling benefit significantly from such targeted interventions, which address various cognitive and educational factors impacting

spelling proficiency.

Table 1. *Spelling Difficulties in Elementary School Pre-Test*

<i>Pre-Test Score</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
11	1	2.86%
13	1	2.86%
17	2	5.71%
18	1	2.86%
22	2	5.71%
23	1	2.86%
25	1	2.86%
26	1	2.86%
28	1	2.86%
35	3	8.57%
37	3	8.57%
38	1	2.86%
41	1	2.86%
42	1	2.86%
43	2	5.71%
45	1	2.86%
48	2	5.71%
51	4	11.43%
52	1	2.86%
53	2	5.71%
55	1	2.86%
57	1	2.86%
61	1	2.86%
Total	35	100.00%
Overall Mean		13.97
Mean		37.74%
Percentage		
Score		
Description		Low

Presented in Table 1 are the results of the pretest, indicating the performance level of 35 students in the experimental group in vocabulary problems. The overall average score for the group was 13.97. The highest score was achieved by one student, representing 11.43% of the total. In contrast, the lowest score was recorded by fourteen students, making up 2.86% of the group. The most frequently occurring score was obtained by seventeen students, accounting for 2.86% of the total. These results indicate a diverse range of performance levels within the group, with a notable concentration of students around the most frequent score. The mean percentage score shown in the table above, is 13.97, which indicates low performance by the students in the pretest. These measures describe that the spelling skills of the students did not meet expectations.

Before the intervention was implemented, as detailed in Table 1, the pretest score was 13.97, which is classified as low. This indicates that the students' spelling abilities were below expectations. The low score suggests that fourth graders have limited exposure to the spelling, making it challenging for them to understand unfamiliar words. To support the findings, Wolter and Apel (2019); Ehri (2017) emphasize the challenges faced by elementary learners in mastering spelling due to a variety of cognitive and educational factors. The students who struggle with spelling often lack a clear understanding of the morphemic structure of words, which includes prefixes, suffixes, and root words.

Moreover, these findings align with prior research by Divani et al. (2018) which emphasize that elementary school teachers often encounter difficulties in building a solid foundation in spelling due to diverse cognitive challenges faced by students. These include issues with memory, phonological processing, and the application of spelling rules, which necessitate comprehensive and adaptive teaching strategies to meet individual student needs. explicit instruction in phonics is essential to support these students. Such instruction should focus on the systematic teaching of sound-letter correspondences, blending, and segmenting sounds to help students develop strong phonological processing skills

Furthermore, recent research by Altamimi (2019) states that, the spelling errors made by elementary students stem from the detrimental effects of their educational system and syllabus. It suggests that the syllabus neglects to emphasize the significance of spelling rules and techniques. Hence, when writing in English, learners often rely on their native language, which can contribute to inadequate spelling skills.

Additionally, some spelling issues arise from a lack of familiarity with writing, listening, reading, and speaking rules in English. These deficiencies in understanding fundamental language rules can further exacerbate challenges in mastering spelling proficiency in English. Therefore, addressing these gaps in knowledge and providing targeted instruction on language rules can significantly improve spelling competence among learners.

Post-Test Result

Table 2 reveals a significant improvement in the spelling abilities of the students after the Letter Blocks intervention, with an overall mean score of 71.80. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing students' spelling skills. According to Educational Core, interactive and engaging methods, such as using letter tiles and other manipulatives object, significantly enhance students' spelling abilities by providing concrete experiences that support phonemic awareness and orthographic knowledge. This also align with prior research by Donald (2021) that hands-on approach allows students to physically manipulate letters and sounds, reinforcing their learning through multi-sensory engagement help students recognize and apply spelling rules, thus enhancing their long-term retention and application of spelling skills.

Table 1. Spelling Difficulties in Elementary School Post-Test

<i>Post-Test Score</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
40	1	2.86%
48	1	2.86%
52	1	2.86%
54	1	2.86%
55	1	2.86%
56	1	2.86%
65	4	11.43%
66	1	2.86%
69	1	2.86%
74	2	5.71%
75	5	14.29%
77	2	5.71%
78	4	11.43%
79	2	5.71%
80	3	8.57%
81	1	2.86%
82	1	2.86%
86	1	2.86%
88	1	2.86%
89	1	2.86%
Total	35	100.00%
Overall Mean		11.59

Presented in Table 2 are the results of the posttest, indicating the performance levels of 35 students in the experimental group in spelling difficulties. The overall average score for the group was 71.80. The highest score was achieved by five students, representing 14.29% of the total. In contrast, the lowest score was recorded by one student, making up 2.86% of the group. The most frequently occurring score was obtained by six students, accounting for 2.86% of the total. These results indicate a diverse range of performance levels within the group, with a notable concentration of students around the most frequent score. The mean percentage score of the students, shown in the table above, is 11.59, which indicates average performance by the students in the post-test. These measures describe that the spelling skills of the students were high.

Providing frequent and varied practice opportunities for students to apply their spelling knowledge. This might involve spelling games, interactive writing exercises, and regular spelling tests that incorporate words used in different contexts. Such varied practice helps reinforce learning and allows students to transfer their spelling skills to various writing situations. Hands-on activities help reinforce learning by engaging multiple senses. To support this, Divani et al., (2018) stated that students might physically manipulate letters to form words, which can enhance their understanding of word structures and improve their spelling skills.

The finding of this study is also supported by Graham et al. (2017), that practical exercises, which often involve activities such as manipulating tactile objects, interactive games, and kinesthetic learning experiences, offer learners opportunities to actively engage with spelling concepts beyond traditional rote memorization. For instance, it discovered that interactive and entertaining techniques, such the use of letter tiles and other manipulative, greatly improve children' spelling skills by giving them real-world experiences that reinforce orthographic knowledge and phonemic awareness. Students may physically handle letters and sounds using this hands-on technique, which reinforces their learning through multisensory engagement.

In addition, recent research by Esposito (2022) emphasize that mastering spelling holds significant importance for children's writing development. The National Curriculum in England outlines spelling lists corresponding to each year group in primary education, highlighting the significance of spelling instruction.

Despite this emphasis, there is limited understanding of teachers' perspectives on teaching spelling and the instructional methods employed in primary schools across England. This study aims to fill this gap by examining various approaches to teaching spelling in primary education settings. By shedding light on teachers' experiences and instructional strategies, the study seeks to enhance our understanding of effective practices in spelling instruction.

Table 3. Significant Difference between Pre-test and Post-test

Type of Test	N	df	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Decision $\alpha=0.05$
Pre-Test	35	34	37.74	13.97	-22.031	< .001	Significant
Post-Test	35		71.80	11.59			

Presented in table 3 was the result of the significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores, $t(34) = -22.031$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($< .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$), the null hypothesis is being rejected. There is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test.

A paired t-test was conducted to determine the level of performance in spelling performance among 35 students during pretest. The t-value obtained was -22.031 , indicating a substantial difference in the scores before and after the intervention or treatment related to spelling abilities acquisition. This large negative t-value suggests a strong effect of the treatment on the students' ability to spell. It indicates that there is a significant improvement in the students' scores from the pretest to the post-test, with the post-test scores being much higher on average. Overall, a t-value of -22.031 in this context indicates a highly significant and positive impact of the intervention or treatment on the students' performance in terms of spelling. The p-value was found to be less than 0.001, with a p-value of less than 0.001, the results are considered statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. This implies that the improvement in vocabulary performance from the pretest to the post-test is unlikely to have occurred by chance.

In connection with the result, Stahl, S.A., & Nagy, W.E. (2020) repeated exposure to words is important because it allows students to encounter vocabulary in a variety of circumstances, allowing them to understand the entire range of a word's meanings and applications. Each time a learner comes across a word, they learn more about its subtleties, connotations, and proper situations for its application. This approach helps to establish the term in their memory, increasing the likelihood that they will be able to use it appropriately in the future.

Various aspects have been discovered through multiple previous investigations done by many academics, including as traditional teaching technique, family history, socioeconomic background, and inadequate exposure to English. Environment, a lack of engaging and appropriate media (learning materials and instruments), poor motivation and interest, as well as students' perspectives and attitudes toward the learning process. As a result, many teachers require additional teaching strategies to supplement their reliance on the textbook serves as the sole source of teaching content. As a result, students feel bored and discouraged with passive learning style stated by Kusuma et al. (2017).

A study by Blachowicz and Fisher (2020) revealed the importance of frequent spelling exercise in providing learners with repeated exposure to new words and their meanings, which helps to reinforce their learning and memory of these words. This consistent practice allows students to incorporate new vocabulary into their existing linguistic framework, boosting their ability to use these terms correctly and confidently in a variety of circumstances. As students participate in these activities, they not only learn new words but also how to use them properly, improving their overall language skills.

Additionally, Depth of Processing Theory stated by Craik, & Tulving, (2021) mentioned that students engaging with words on a deeper level result in stronger memory traces, making the word simpler to recall later. This is because deeper processing necessitates more detailed encoding, which improves long-term memory retention. When words are deeply absorbed, their meanings become more fully comprehended. This deeper understanding enables greater text comprehension and more accurate word use in conversation.

Conclusions

The study on the implementation of the letter blocks intervention in addressing spelling difficulties in elementary school students specifically grade-4 learners reveals a multifaceted approach and effective strategies employed to enhance spelling proficiency. Key themes identified include difficulties with phonemic awareness, efficient letter-sound correspondence, fostering independent spelling skills, improving motivation, reducing anxiety, and promoting confidence. These themes underscore the complex interplay of cognitive, psychological, and educational factors influencing students' spelling abilities. The intervention addressed existing challenges in traditional spelling instruction, such as lack of engagement, insufficient resources, and the need for individualized learning approaches. Furthermore, the positive impact on students' confidence and motivation highlights the importance of holistic support systems to address both academic and emotional aspects of learning.

Coping Mechanisms adopted by Elementary Schools that implementing of letter blocks intervention demonstrates a holistic and effective strategy in addressing spelling difficulties among elementary school students. Utilizing engaging learning resources, structured time management, external support, self-care practices, goal-oriented motivation, habitual reading, and an inclusive learning environment, this approach illustrates a proactive and resourceful method for overcoming educational challenges. These strategies not only facilitated academic success but also contributed to personal growth amidst unprecedented challenges. Insights from this intervention highlight the importance of continued parental involvement, additional resources for teachers and students, regular assessments of learning readiness, financial assistance, and considerate academic policies. The findings align with broader educational research advocating for the benefits of blended learning, the crucial role of technology in education, and the need to bridge the digital divide. This study underscores the resilience and adaptability of students in navigating educational changes, pointing towards the

necessity for institutional support, technological accessibility, and flexible learning environments to enhance academic achievement and well-being.

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